

MOIN4Herbie deliverable 9 - Prototypical publication of Herbie metadata along sensor data via STA

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Figure 1: MOIN4Herbie logo

Introduction

Purpose of this document

This document contains deliverable 9 *Prototypical publication of Herbie metadata along sensor data via STA* of the project MOIN4Herbie - Maintenance Ontology and audit log Integration for Herbie funded by the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC). Deliverable 9 is part of work packages 5 *Integration of Herbie metadata in sensor data streams*. In this document, the sensor metadata from O2A registry along with sensor maintenance metadata from Herbie and sensor data stream are published on STA interface.

Background

The MOIN4Herbie project extends Herbie, the electronic laboratory notebook to document the sensor maintenance activities. Accurate maintenance documentation requires access to detailed device metadata, including sensor characteristics (e.g., name, type, serial number, description), deployment locations, and the environmental parameters measured by each sensor. Herbie does not require device metadata input from the users, it maintain its own copies of these metadata. Instead, the system integrates with the O2A Registry API to dynamically obtain the relevant metadata. These data are then converted into the RDF format required by Herbie using the Registry2RDF module [1], which transforms registry metadata into the Resource Description Framework (RDF) structure [2]. This interoperability-focused approach ensures data consistency, reduces duplication, and supports seamless integration of Herbie with external device metadata sources.

O2A Registry

The O2A Registry provides a structured, persistent, and transparent system for documenting scientific platforms, sensors, and research equipment. Developed at the Alfred Wegener Institute, it serves as a repository for recording and storing device metadata, accessible via both a user interface and an API [3].

It captures key instrument details such as the device name, type, description, serial number, model, and manufacturer. The registry also includes contact fields for storing information about the people associated with a device. It includes the documentation of parameters, including a short name generally used by scientists, a human-readable name, links to controlled vocabularies from standardized vocabulary sources such as PANGAEA or NERC, and the corresponding units. Parameter-specific properties, such as lower and upper bounds, can also be defined.

In addition, it allows the position of a device to be recorded using either absolute or relative coordinates which could be helpful to locate it on a vessel and it is possible to store supplementary information such as external links, DOIs, calibration sheets, manuals, and images of the item itself or its installation environment.

Overview Contacts Events Parameters Properties Frame Resources Images Collections Fields

O2A REGISTRY: Metadata for salinity sensor Salinity Sensor at current version. Alfred Wegener Institut Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research. <https://hdl.handle.net/10013/registry.55fecad7-1bc3-49a0-8ca2-90aeb39df417>

Long name *	Salinity Sensor	Model	
Short name *	SBE45_A	Manufacturer	
Type *	salinity sensor i	Serial	
Code	station:tesperhude:ferrybox_tesperhude:sbe45_a	Asset number	
Status *	public i	Parent item	station:tesperhude:ferrybox_tesperhude 🔗
Description			
An instrument designed for the continuous measurement of seawater temperature and salinity, usually associated with shipborne measurements in the upper 5m of the water column.			

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Figure 2: Metadata of a salinity sensor in Tesperhude station

STA

The OGC SensorThings API (STA API) is an open standard created by the Open Geospatial Consortium to provide a unified, lightweight, and geospatial-enabled way to connect Internet of Things (IoT) devices, their data, and related applications over the web. It follows REST principles and uses efficient JSON. The API is built around a very general data model composed of entities such as Thing, Sensor, Location, Datastream, Observation, and FeatureOfInterest allowing for consistent representation and exchange of many types of sensor data from single observations to environmental monitoring or lab analysis.

However, many applications, especially those in the environmental sciences, require additional metadata. This includes, for example, information about responsible persons and affiliations, data providers, detailed information on sensor deployments or maintenance events. While STA recommends describing such information in the properties fields of its entities, this approach often results in inconsistent and non-interoperable metadata. To address this, the HMC-STAMPLATE project developed a set of well-defined JSON Schemas that standardize the usage of STA properties. These schemas enable richer and more consistent metadata integration into STA infrastructures in a structured and interoperable way.

Approach

Metadata

Metadata from O2A Registry: The sensor metadata itself is not duplicated in Herbie. Instead, the required metadata is retrieved from the O2A Registry via its REST API and transformed from JSON into RDF, which is the format used by Herbie. This transformation is carried out using the Registry2RDF module developed as part of Deliverable 7.

From the O2A Registry, we query metadata such as the sensor name and sensor type, as this provides the necessary context about which sensor or device the maintenance activity recorded in Herbie refers to. Since multiple similar sensors may exist within a system, it is also important to identify where a given sensor is installed. For this reason, information about the parent items is also retrieved from O2A.

It is equally necessary to include contact names, as this metadata is essential for identifying who performed the maintenance activity. The parameters measured by the sensors are also incorporated, as it is needed for maintenance activities such as sampling or calibration.

Metadata in Herbie: Sensor maintenance metadata provides temporal context that is often critical for data interpretation. For instance, if a salinity sensor's data suddenly shifts, knowing that a calibration event or sensor cleaning event took place on that date allows one to attribute the change to maintenance rather than an environmental phenomenon. By explicitly logging events, we preserve this context.

Herbie records metadata for a range of maintenance activities, including cleaning, deep cleaning, calibration, sampling, deployment, decommissioning, repair, and replacement.

Cleaning refers to general cleaning activities carried out either on the sensor itself or on the sensor frame. Deep cleaning can be very specific to the sensor type and station. It may be performed on site or externally and can involve different categories, such as the procedure was chemical or mechanical.

Calibration metadata includes information such as the location where the calibration is performed and the responsible organization, if the calibration is conducted externally, or the responsible person. The specific sensor undergoing calibration can be selected, and related sampling activities may also be associated with it, also includes whether the procedure involves drift measurements or a full calibration, the dilution applied, the measurements recorded for each dilution level, additional notes, and the time at which the calibration was performed.

Through continuous discussions with end users during the development phase, we designed it not only to capture the required maintenance activity details, but also to include planning and memo components. This allows scientists to use it as an electronic lab notebook in the full sense of the term.

Figure 3: Calibration form

Linking Herbie to O2A registry: In Herbie we record sensor maintenance metadata in great detail, we want to also add some of these maintenance information to sensor metadata in O2A registry so that the sensor has its whole lifecycle metadata stored.

Figure 4: Cleaning action added to o2a from herbie

Rather than Herbie operating as an isolated notebook, it acts as part of a larger ecosystem: tapping into the registry for existing sensor metadata and contributing back with new or updated metadata related to its maintenance.

We link maintenance activities to the registry through the Events tab, as it serves a similar purpose within the O2A Registry. Event type categories defined in the registry, such as calibration, sampling, and repair,

were adapted for use in Herbie with possibility to add further information in the description, the mapping between the maintenance activities of Herbie and events types of O2A registry is shown in Table 1. In the ontology, these maintenance activity types are represented as subclasses of device action which is a subclass of Actuation, forming the basis for the mapping between Herbie and registry.

Herbie – Maintenance tasks	O2A Registry – Event types
Calibration	Calibration
Cleaning	Maintenance
Deep Cleaning	Maintenance
Deployment	Deployment
Repair	Maintenance
Sampling	Information

Table 1: Linking maintenance tasks between Herbie and O2A registry

The relevant metadata is queried from Herbie using SPARQL [5]. A script then transforms the retrieved data into the JSON structure required by the registry before it is pushed to the registry.

A subset of maintenance metadata is transferred to the registry. This includes, for example, the type of maintenance activity carried out, such as sampling, as well as a label. It is also possible to include the start and end date of the activity and to record additional notes, for example about sampling, in the description field as shown in the Figure 5.

Figure 5: Linking Herbie to O2A registry

Publishing metadata along with data on STA: Data in our time series database follow the extended property schema developed in the STAMPLATE project. The STAMPLATE schema defines metadata extensions for *Things* (i.e. the parent item of a sensor, e.g. Tesperhude Station or Boknis Eck), *Sensors* (e.g. a specific sensor or a specific lab where analysis are carried out), *ObservedProperties* (the measured parameters), *Observations* (the time and value of the measured/observed parameter) and *Datastreams* (which tie together Things, Sensors, ObservedProperties and Observations). In the context of MOIN4Herbie, the *Sensor* entity is the most important.

```

▼ 0:
  @iot.selfLink: "https://timeseries-test.geomar.de/boknis/FROST-Server/v1.1/Sensors(1011)"
  @iot.id: 1011
  name: "GEOMAR Laboratory Boknis Eck Bange"
  description: "GEOMAR Laboratory Boknis Eck Bange"
  encodingType: "application/json"
  metadata: '{ "source": "O2A Registry", "registryItem": "https://registry.o2a-data.de/rest/v2/items/9d8f1337-dc98-4fb4-a340-6f1e31e1ff5f", "identifier": "9d8f1337-dc98-4fb4-a340-6f1e31e1ff5f", "type": "Sensor"}'

  ▼ properties:
    @id: "https://registry.o2a-data.de/rest/v2/items/9d8f1337-dc98-4fb4-a340-6f1e31e1ff5f"
    urn: "station:boknis_eck:lab_boknis_eck_bange"
    isVirtual: false
    shortName: "lab_boknis_eck_bange"
    variantOf: "laboratory"
    identifier: "9d8f1337-dc98-4fb4-a340-6f1e31e1ff5f"
    registryId: 12884
    isVariantOf: "laboratory"
    Datastreams@iot.navigationLink: "https://timeseries-test.geomar.de/boknis/FROST-Server/v1.1/Sensors(1011)/Datastreams"

```

Figure 6: Representation of a sensor with links to O2A in the STA database

The example above shows the representation of a Boknis Eck laboratory as an STA Sensor. The metadata shown there originates from the O2A registry, i.e. the sensors are first created there and are synced with our STA database later. Essential metadata, such as identifier and serial number, are duplicated from the O2A registry, while other information is accessed by following the links to the sensor in O2A.

In its current form, the STAMPLATE schema originally had no provision for including maintenance metadata directly in STA. This limitation has now been addressed: we implemented a structured extension that allows sensor maintenance information from Herbie to be published alongside sensor metadata in the STA Sensor entity. The maintenance events that were previously pushed only to the O2A Registry are now also replicated within the STA properties object, where they are stored as an array of maintenance entries following the extended schema. This ensures that maintenance activities—such as cleaning, calibration, sampling, and repairs—are directly accessible within STA without compromising compatibility with existing STAMPLATE structures. As shown in Figure 7, the maintenance history of a sensor is now visible directly in the STA interface, enabling seamless traceability across Herbie, O2A, and STA.

Figure 7: Linking Maintenance metadata in STA

Significance of the Integration between Herbie, O2A Registry, and STA API: This integration provides several key benefits:

- **End-to-End Transparency:** Enables full traceability from lab notebook entries in Herbie to devices in the O2A Registry and observations in STA, increasing the traceability and data reliability.
- **Data Consistency:** Ensures alignment with standardized metadata and vocabularies across platforms and institutions.
- **Interoperability and Accessibility:** Publishing to the SensorThings API greatly broadens the accessibility of the data.
- **FAIR Compliance:** Supports Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable data through structured metadata and standardized access.

Discussion and Conclusion

Integrating sensor maintenance metadata from Herbie with sensor metadata from the O2A Registry, and publishing it together with observation data via the SensorThings API creates a robust, efficient ecosystem for sensor data management.

By capturing high-quality metadata at the source through ontologies and SHACL, and making it available in a standardized and accessible form, this approach ensures consistency across systems and enhances data transparency. As a result, it improves the reliability of sensor data for scientists and stakeholders, supporting analysis and decision-making.

References

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